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The GFP Thermal Shift assay for screening ligand and lipid interactions to Solute Carrier transporters

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1 Solute Carrier (SLC) transporters represent the second-largest fraction of the
2 membrane proteome after G-protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs), but have been
3 under-utilised as drug targets and the function of many members of this family is
4 still unknown. They are technically challenging to work with as they are difficult
5 to express and highly dynamic, making them unstable in detergent solution. Many
6 SLCs lack known inhibitors that could be utilized for stabilisation. Furthermore,
7 as they bind their physiological substrates with high μM to low mM affinities,
8 binding and transport assays have proven to be particularly challenging to
9 implement. Previously, we reported a GFP-based method for the overexpression
10 and purification of membrane proteins in *S. cerevisiae*. Here, we extend this
11 expression platform with the GFP-thermal-shift (GFP-TS) assay, which is a
12 simplified version of fluorescence-detection size-exclusion chromatography
13 (FSEC-TS) that combines the sample versatility of FSEC-TS, with the high-
14 throughput capability of dye-based thermal-shift assays. We demonstrate how
15 GFP-TS can be used for detecting specific ligand interactions and their affinities
16 of SLC transporter fusions in crude detergent solubilised membranes. We further
17 show how GFP-TS can be employed on purified SLC transporter fusions to screen
18 for specific lipid-protein interactions, which is an important complement to native
19 mass spectrometry approaches that cannot cope easily with crude lipid-mixture
20 preparations. This protocol is simple to perform and can be followed by
21 researchers with a basic background in protein chemistry.

22

23 INTRODUCTION

24

25 Membrane proteins are fundamental for cell survival and represent attractive targets for
26 drug discovery. Despite their importance, membrane proteins are technically
27 challenging to work with, thus hampering elucidation of their function. Such an
28 example is the Solute Carrier (SLC) transporter family, which makes up the second
29 largest fraction of the membrane proteins after GPCRs^{1,2}. SLC transporters are critical
30 to cell homeostasis and fundamental to many physiological processes, such as transport
31 of glucose, peptides, ions, neurotransmitters and drugs in every cell type and
32 organelle^{3,4}. Despite their biological significance, many SLCs have no known function

1 and are under-utilized as drug targets^{1,2,5,6}. The pharmaceutical development of
2 compounds targeting SLCs such as the anti-diabetic drug Jardiance, a small molecule
3 inhibitor of the sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 (SGLT2)⁷, epitomizes the potential
4 benefits of targeting SLCs. Interest in the physiological role and potential drugability
5 of SLCs has therefore risen, calling for further systematic characterization^{1,5}.

6

7 Unlike channels and GPCRs for which there are already well established high-
8 throughput screening technologies^{8,9}, detection of specific substrate-SLC transport
9 pairing is challenging *in vivo* and typically requires the availability of isotope- or
10 fluorescently-labelled compounds and well-known inhibitors for validation, due to
11 overlapping substrate specificities of different transporters^{10,11}. In addition to this
12 limitation the cell can, i) have several complementary transport systems, ii) metabolize
13 the transported compound, and iii) localize the SLC to internal compartment
14 membranes inaccessible for activity studies^{10,12}. While bioinformatic analysis and
15 genome-wide RNA interference (RNAi) screens and^{4,5} CRISPR knockout and knockin
16 experiments can provide useful insights into potential substrates^{6,7}, it still remains
17 necessary in most cases to validate such interactions using *in vitro*-based binding and
18 transporter assays. A requirement for *in vitro*-based assays is overexpression and
19 purification of the SLC transporter protein. However, like many membrane proteins,
20 SLC transporters are often difficult to produce and are typically unstable in detergent
21 solution, making them difficult to isolate¹³. GFP-based tags have become a mainstream
22 approach that facilitates homologue screening and construct modification to enable
23 isolation of well-expressed and detergent stable membrane proteins⁸⁻¹³. Previously, we
24 outlined a GFP-based screening platform to optimize the expression, stability and
25 purification of eukaryotic membrane proteins in *S. cerevisiae*^{14,15}. This platform has
26 since been used to carry out functional and structural investigation for a number of SLC
27 transporters and other types of membrane proteins¹⁵⁻¹⁹.

28

29 Here, we extend the *S. cerevisiae* GFP-based protein production platform with the GFP-
30 TS assay for monitoring ligand interactions of SLC transporters using either crude
31 detergent-solubilized membranes or purified samples²⁰. The GFP-TS assay offers an
32 attractive complementary approach to characterize SLC transporters by bridging the

1 gap between the relative ambiguity of large-scale phenotypic screening and challenging
2 transport assays in proteoliposomes using purified components.

3

4 **Development of the GFP-TS assay for monitoring ligand-protein interactions**

5 An attractive high-throughput strategy to functionally characterize SLC transporters is
6 to screen for ligand binding rather than transport. Specific binders could turn out to be
7 *bona fide* substrates or at least inhibitors, which are nevertheless useful for e.g.
8 functional characterization of transporters in cell-based assays. Moreover, knowledge
9 that a ligand binds serves as a useful positive control to facilitate characterization by
10 other methods, such as the solid-supported membrane (SSM)-based
11 electrophysiology¹⁶ and proteoliposome transport assays¹⁷. Arguably, the most
12 successful high-throughput label-free binding technologies are thermal-shift assays
13 (TSA), which are based on measuring a ligand-induced change in the thermostability
14 of the target^{18,19}. The most common TSA is differential scanning fluorimetry (DSF),
15 otherwise commonly referred to as thermofluor assay, which monitors heat induced
16 protein unfolding by including an environmentally sensitive fluorescent dye that binds
17 to the protein and increases fluorescence as the protein unfolds¹⁸⁻²⁰. For membrane
18 proteins, the sulfhydryl-binding dye N-[4-(7-diethylamino-4-methyl-3-
19 coumarinyl)phenyl]maleimide (CPM) has been successfully used for monitoring
20 unfolding and ligand binding to many different types of membrane proteins^{11,13,21}.
21 Recently, the CPM assay was successfully applied to detect specific substrate binding
22 in a library of different compounds to mitochondrial SLC transporters¹¹.

23 Whilst our GFP-based overexpression and purification pipeline in *S. cerevisiae*
24 facilitates the isolation of SLC transporters for the CPM assay¹³, the intrinsic
25 fluorescence of the green fluorescent protein (GFP)-fusion partner also includes the
26 possibility to monitor thermal denaturation by fluorescence-detection size-exclusion
27 chromatography (FSEC-TS)²². Encouragingly, FSEC-TS is also compatible with
28 unpurified samples for detecting drug or ligand binding²². This is an advantage over
29 dye-based unfolding assays, which cannot cope with unpurified samples, require large
30 amounts of purified protein, and sometimes give uninterpretable results²³. There are
31 also mixed reports for the suitability of the CPM-dye for monitoring lipid-protein
32 interactions^{24,25}, as the interactions detected in principle could be a result of competition

1 between the hydrophobic dye and lipids. Furthermore, in an unpurified sample the
2 target resides in a more native-like lipid environment, which presents an attractive
3 advantage for cases when it is difficult to purify the protein, or when lipid-driven
4 modulation of drug binding could be an important factor ²⁶.

5

6 Despite these advantages, FSEC-TS is a relatively low to mid-throughput method, as it
7 relies on a size-exclusion step for separating the protein peak from heat-induced
8 aggregates at each temperature, which remain fluorescent. Here, we show that the SEC
9 step can be replaced by centrifugation, if the short-chain detergent octyl- β -D-glucoside
10 (OG) is added prior to heating to force precipitation of heat-induced aggregates to
11 accelerate and simplify the overall procedure, resulting in GFP-TS (Fig. 1)²⁷. The
12 melting temperatures (T_m) measured by GFP-TS in crude-detergent solubilized
13 membranes are comparable to the T_m values calculated by FSEC-TS and the unfolding
14 rates measured by the CPM assay with purified transporters (Fig. 2a–d)²⁷. Importantly,
15 as outlined here, the GFP-TS assay is transferrable to a 96-well format and given its
16 simplicity should be transferrable to already established high-throughput (HTP)
17 thermofluor-based screening strategies. Downstream from initial substrate
18 identification, the GFP-TS assay can also be used to analyze specific substrate-SLC
19 transporter interactions^{27,28}.

20

21 **Comparison with other methods**

22 There are other TSA that are compatible with unpurified samples, in particular, the
23 cellular thermal shift assay (CETSA), which can monitor a change in protein thermal
24 stability upon ligand binding in intact cells or lysates^{18,29}. The combination of CETSA
25 principle with high resolution MS (MS-CETSA), also known as thermal proteome
26 profiling 'TPP' has proven a powerful method³⁰, which uses high-resolution mass
27 spectrometry (MS) for calculating melting curves and subsequent ligand-protein
28 induced thermostabilization³¹. Nevertheless, without recombinant protein expression,
29 lowly abundant membrane proteins have proven challenging for CETSA and TPP with
30 few *de novo* targets identified^{32,33}. Those ligands that have been paired to a membrane
31 protein target have had very high (nM) binding affinities^{32,33}. The major drawback of

1 CETSA for deorphanization of a single target is that it requires the availability of
2 highly-specific antibodies, which predominantly recognize the folded state of the
3 membrane protein³². Given that many membrane proteins and SLC transporters lack
4 specific and high-quality antibodies, overexpression of the target in a well-folded state
5 becomes essential, which is facilitated by GFP-based tagging. Moreover, the GFP-TS
6 assay has fewer technical steps than CETSA and facilitates downstream purification,
7 which is a requirement for studying lipid-protein interactions.

8

9 In addition to ligands and substrates, specific lipids are often found to regulate the
10 function of SLC transporters and membrane proteins in general³⁴⁻³⁷. Recently, mass
11 spectrometry (MS) has gained traction as a tool for probing the intricate connections
12 between membrane proteins and lipids³⁸, shedding light on different lipid binding
13 modes³⁹, lipid-mediated protein stabilization and even thermodynamics and allosteric
14 effects of protein–lipid interactions^{40,41}. Despite its proven usefulness for studying
15 individual protein–lipid contacts and the development towards analyzing more complex
16 mixtures⁴², currently MS, like other spectroscopic and computational approaches, is not
17 well-suited for identifying specific interactions in native membranes or in high-
18 throughput formats, impeding large-scale investigations.

19

20 Here, we further demonstrate that FSEC-TS and the GFP-TS assay can be applied to
21 screen for and detect specific lipid interactions of purified SLC transporters. Although
22 the simpler GFP-TS method increases sample capacity and makes it possible to screen
23 and assess hundreds of ligands simultaneously, FSEC remains an important initial
24 quality check for the GFP-TS assay. Furthermore, FSEC-TS can be used to further
25 assess if ligands or lipids alter oligomerization of the target²⁷. We have found these
26 indirect GFP-based methods for assessing ligand interactions, to be a particularly useful
27 tool in combination with native MS for confirming and mapping specific lipid
28 interactions to SLC transporters, which could otherwise be perturbed when assessed by
29 thermofluor dyes^{27,43}.

30

31

1 **Overview**

2 The current protocol (a schematic overview is shown in Fig. 1) begins with a yeast
3 membrane fraction harbouring the heterologous overexpressed GFP-fusion, which was
4 prepared according to the previous publication ¹⁴. Initially, the target-containing
5 membranes are solubilized in the mild detergent DDM, and the sample is assessed for
6 its suitability for GFP-TS by FSEC (steps 1-5). Once protein quality has been
7 established, the next procedure is to assess target thermostability in membranes (steps
8 6-12). Briefly, the target is solubilized in the mild detergent DDM, aliquoted, the harsh
9 detergent OG added, heated over a range of different temperatures from 10-90°C, and
10 then pelleted to remove heat-induced aggregates. The fluorescence remaining in the
11 supernatant from the non-aggregated GFP-fusion is then measured in a plate reader, and
12 the apparent melting temperature T_m is calculated. Downstream, we outline the
13 optimization steps that might be required on a case-by-case basis, prior to large-scale
14 ligand screening. For example, the addition of the solvent DMSO to assess potential
15 interference with detecting interactions with ligands that have been stored in DMSO
16 (steps 13-21), and the optimal temperature for screening for ligand interactions (steps
17 22-29). Once these parameters have been adjusted, ligand screening can be conducted
18 by GFP-TS using detergent-solubilized membranes (steps 30-38). Moreover, affinity
19 estimates can be obtained simply by heating the GFP-fusion with increasing ligand
20 concentrations (steps 39-48). GFP-TS can also be used to rapidly assess how mutations
21 in the protein affect ligand binding, which is most optimal when structural information
22 is available (steps 49-54).

23 Overall, the GFP-TS is applicable for GFP-fusions in either crude membranes or as
24 purified fusions, with minimal adaptations between the two sample types. In the end of
25 this protocol we outline the similar steps for obtaining an apparent T_m using purified
26 material (steps 55-57) and how the detergent purified protein can be used to screen for
27 specific lipid-protein interactions (steps 58-66).

28

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31

1 **Experimental design**

2 *Starting material: target-protein in membranes*

3 As outlined in the preceding protocol¹⁴, the targets and constructs are first optimized
4 for monodispersity in the mild detergent (*n*-Dodecyl- β -D-maltopyranoside) DDM by
5 FSEC⁴⁴. To omit the FSEC for analysis by GFP-TS, the amount of free GFP should not
6 exceed 30 % of the protein-GFP peak to ensure the melting temperature stays within a
7 10% error (Fig. 2e); this is because free GFP is stable and will not be precipitated by
8 heating, masking the signal reduction of the protein-GFP fusion. In addition, aggregates
9 formed during target overexpression should not be more than 30% of the folded protein-
10 fusion peak as they could also potentially mask unfolding, since the GFP-TS assay is
11 optimized to remove heat-induced aggregates, and not aggregates present prior to
12 heating.

13 *Addition of OG to DDM-solubilized protein-GFP fusions*

14 OG is considered a “harsh” detergent, as its addition tends to cause protein aggregates
15 to precipitate rather than stay in solution¹³. As OG is added to all samples, it is
16 recommended for experiments to proceed swiftly after addition of OG to decrease
17 unwanted time-cumulative protein aggregation. On average, melting temperatures with
18 DDM + OG are about 7.5 °C lower than with DDM only²⁸. Although the addition of
19 OG might not be strictly necessary in all cases, on average the apparent T_m values
20 obtained with GFP-TS are more comparable to FSEC-TS when OG is included (Fig.
21 2b, c, f and Table 1). For this reason, the GFP-TS assay has been optimized with
22 inclusion of OG (Fig. 3a). We observe a strong correlation between GFP-TS and the
23 CPM assay when OG is included ($R^2 = 0.78$, Fig. 3b). Furthermore, an average T_m of
24 47°C was estimated by thermal proteome profiling (TPP) of 371 membrane proteins in
25 a human cell-line when proteins were solubilized in a mild detergent³¹, suggesting that
26 many targets should be stable enough in DDM + OG detergents. However, in cases
27 when the T_m drops to less than 30 °C with OG present, adjustments to this protocol
28 might be necessary, such as reducing the final concentration of OG from 1.0 to 0.5%
29 w/v (Table 1, 2).

30

31

1 *Heating block vs thermal cycler for heating*

2 Initial experiments were carried out using a heating block. However, to further develop
3 our assay and render it suitable for high-throughput applications, we adapted the
4 protocol to use a thermal cycler, which allows for processing of up to 96 samples
5 simultaneously. Moreover, gradient thermal cyclers allow generation of full melting
6 curves faster and with the same accuracy as a standard heating block (Fig. 3c).
7 Therefore, our procedure instructs for the use of a gradient or conventional thermal
8 cycler. However, all experiments can be performed using a heating block yielding the
9 same quality if a thermal cycler is unavailable.

10 *Assay check-points for ligand screening*

11 In addition to measuring the melting temperature of the target protein, GFP-TS can be
12 applied to screen for interacting ligands. To ensure the success of such a screen, it is
13 critical that appropriate control experiments are carried out. Typically, ligands are
14 dissolved in organic solvents such as dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) or ethanol.
15 Consequently, prior to performing a ligand screen, the possibility of solvent-induced
16 effects on the target protein stability must be determined. By monitoring the protein
17 stability over a range of solvent concentrations, potential solvent effects can be
18 identified and eliminated (Fig. 3d). As already established, GFP-TS is a
19 thermostability-based assay, which means a temperature-induced destabilization of the
20 system is necessary when screening for ligands. For GFP-TS, potential stabilizing
21 effects of ligands are more prominent when the remaining protein signal is roughly 20
22 - 50% compared to that of the unheated and untreated control. To identify this window
23 of reduced signal intensity, it is recommended that a range of temperatures are
24 investigated prior to large-scale ligand screening (Fig. 3e).

25

26 **Limitations**

27 The use of GFP as a protein marker has become a mainstream approach in protein
28 production and purification systems^{14,45-47}, making GFP-TS an attractive and easily
29 applicable option for many laboratories. This offers a great amount of adaptability
30 considering the intrinsic stability of GFP, as well as the many varieties of GFP that have
31 been engineered overtime. At the same time, one should carefully consider the

1 experimental setup which might require optimization, to avoid uninterpretable or
2 inconsistent results. For example, a possible issue arising from protein overexpression
3 is increased protein aggregation, and in the case of GFP-pipelines, cleavage of GFP
4 during target preparation. Since there is no possibility to distinguish between signals
5 from target-GFP aggregates, target-GFP and “free” GFP in the sample, it is important
6 that one first ensures sample quality by FSEC²² prior to this assay to avoid false signal
7 generation or signal masking caused by free GFP, i.e., as also outlined in the proceeding
8 protocol¹⁴

9 The GFP-TS assay relies on the precipitation of heat-induced aggregates through
10 the addition of a relatively harsh detergent β -OG to the mild detergent DDM.
11 Consequently, a degree of protein destabilization due to interaction with OG can
12 be expected. In our experience, if the target remains monodisperse (well-folded)
13 once purified in DDM as previously outlined (ref ¹⁴), then the target will be stable
14 enough for using the GFP-TS assay. Nevertheless, we anticipate that in some cases,
15 the degree of destabilization caused by OG addition might make the target no
16 longer stable enough for GFP-TS ($T_M < 30^\circ\text{C}$). Alternatives to overcome this are
17 offered in the troubleshooting section. Since GFP is no longer fluorescent above
18 76°C , the GFP-TS assay cannot be used to assess membrane proteins with higher
19 melting temperatures. Nevertheless, we have not come across eukaryotic **SLC**
20 transporters that are more stable than 76°C in the presence of DDM and OG
21 detergents.

22 On a general level, thermal shift assays rely on changes of the target thermal
23 stability resulting from interaction with a binder. This approach has been widely
24 explored for structural studies as well as in drug discovery¹⁸. Although particularly
25 useful for large-scale screening, thermal stabilization is not always observed upon
26 ligand binding and thus, the GFP-TS assay, like any other TSAs, is prone to false-
27 negative results^{30,48}. Furthermore, ligand screens conducted on crude material
28 might fail to detect protein-ligand pairing, due to off-target interactions, or ligand
29 modifications caused by other proteins in the system⁴⁹. Consequently, the amount
30 of ligand available for interaction with the target is diminished or no longer
31 recognised. In such cases, purification of the GFP-target might be necessary before
32 application of the GFP-TS assay.

1 **MATERIALS**

2 **BIOLOGICAL MATERIALS**

3 Membrane resuspension containing GFP-fused protein target. See steps 27—32 in
4 Nat. Protoc. 3, 784-798, (2008)¹⁴.

5 **REAGENTS**

6

7 • *n*-Dodecyl- β -D-maltopyranoside (DDM; Anatrace, cat. no. D310)

8

9 • *n*- Octyl- β -D-Glucopyranoside (OG; Anatrace, cat. no. O311)

10

11 • 18:1 1,2-dioleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphate (sodium salt) (DOPA; Avanti,
12 cat. no. 840875)

13

14 • 18:1 (Δ^9 -Cis) 1,2-dioleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phospho-(1'-rac-glycerol) (sodium
15 salt) (DOPG; Avanti, cat. no. 840475)

16

17 • 18:1 (Δ^9 -Cis) 1,2-dioleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DOPC; Avanti,
18 cat. no. 850375P)

19

20 • 18:1 (Δ^9 -Cis) 1,2-dioleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine (DOPE;
21 Avanti, cat. no. 850725)

22

23 • Phosphatidylinositol bis-4,5-phosphate, 1,2-dioctanoyl (PIP2; Larodan,
24 cat. no. 59-1124)

25

26 • Phosphatidylinositol tris-3,4,5-phosphate,1,2-dipalmitoyl (PIP3; Larodan,
27 cat. no. 59-1102)

28

29 • Bicinchoninic acid (BCA) protein assay kit (Pierce, cat. no. 23225)

30

CAUTION: Reagent B in the kit is very toxic to aquatic life. Avoid its release
31 to the environment and dispose of the container and its contents into an
32 approved waste disposal plant.

33

34 **EQUIPMENT**

35

36 • Microfuge 18 Centrifuge, Beckman Coulter (Eppendorf centrifuge).

37

38 • 0.2 mL PCR tubes

39

40 • 96 well PCR plates

41

- 1 • 96-well black optical bottom plate (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. no.
2 265301) or 96-well black plate (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. no. 237105)
3
4 • SpectraMax M2e microplate reader (Molecular Devices) or Fluoroskan
5 microplate reader (Thermo Fisher Scientific)
6
7
8 • ENrich SEC 650 10 × 300 Column (BIO-RAD, cat. no. 7801650)
9
10 • HPLC system (Shimadzu Prominence) equipped with a fluorescent
11 detector unit (RF-20A).
12
13 • Heating block (Eppendorf Thermomixer comfort 1.5mL)
14
15 • Veriti 96-well thermal cycler (Thermo Fisher Scientific)

16

17

18 SOFTWARE

19

- 20 • GraphPad Prism version 7.0 or later, (GraphPad Software, San Diego,
21 California USA, www.graphpad.com)

22

23

24 REAGENT SETUP

25

- 26 • **FSEC buffer** 20 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.5), 150 mM NaCl, 0.03% (w/v)
27 DDM (Can be stored at room temperature for 3 days)
28 • **GFP-TS reaction buffer** 20 mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.5), 150 mM NaCl, 1%
29 (w/v) DDM (in the final reaction volume) (Prepare fresh)
30 • **DDM stock** 10 % (w/v) in H₂O (Can be stored at –20 °C for 6 months, use
31 up in less than 5 freeze-thaw cycles)
32 • **OG stock** 10% (w/v) in H₂O (Can be stored at –20 °C for 6 months, use
33 up in less than 5 freeze-thaw cycles)
34 • **Lipid stocks** 30 mg/mL in 10% (w/v) DDM (Can be stored at –20 °C for
35 6 months, as single-use aliquots of 40 µL)

1 **PROCEDURE**

2

3 **CRITICAL:** All steps should be performed at 4°C or on ice unless otherwise stated.

4

5 **Confirming GFP-fusion quality • Timing 2h 30min**

6 1. Adjust total membrane protein concentration (determined by the BCA assay) to
7 3.5 mg/mL in 1mL by addition of GFP-TS reaction buffer. Solubilize under mild
8 agitation (~ 60 rpm) at 4 °C for 1 h.

9 2. Transfer 100 µL of solubilized material into a single well of a 96-well black
10 plate. Measure GFP fluorescence emission at 512 nm by excitation at 488 nm
11 in a microplate spectrofluorometer. For plate readers with bottom read option,
12 choose this setting. Centrifuge the remaining sample at 100,000g at 4 °C for 45
13 min.

14 3. Measure GFP-fluorescence from 100 µL of supernatant as in step 2. Calculate
15 detergent solubilization efficiency by comparing to the initial fluorescence
16 value obtained in step 2. **CRITICAL STEP:** If the solubilization efficiency is
17 >70%, but the fluorescent signal is weak (less than ten-fold higher than
18 background), the amount of membranes used can be increased to boost the
19 signal-to-noise (Fig. 3f).? **TROUBLESHOOTING**

20 4. Transfer 100 µL of supernatant into an FSEC vial and inject the sample into a
21 Biorad Enrich 650 SEC column (flow rate 1 mL/min) equilibrated in FSEC
22 buffer.

23 5. Analyze the FSEC trace to confirm the target-GFP fusion is the predominant
24 species and any aggregation or free GFP is less than 30% of the total peak
25 height. ? **TROUBLESHOOTING**

26 **Determining melting temperature (T_m) in crude detergent-solubilized**
27 **membranes • Timing 3 h**

28 6. Adjust total membrane protein concentration to at least 3.5 mg/mL in 6.5 mL
29 by addition of GFP-TS reaction buffer. Solubilize under mild agitation at 4 °C
30 for 1 h. **CRITICAL STEP:** When preparing the protein-solubilization mix,
31 subtract the volume of OG that will be added in the following step (10% of the

1 total volume, i.e. solubilization is carried out in $6.5 - 0.65 = 5.85$ mL).?

2 **TROUBLESHOOTING**

3 7. Add 650 μ L OG stock (for a final concentration of 1% w/v) and mix sample
4 carefully by inverting the tube.

5 8. Aliquot 120 μ L of the solubilized membrane solution with OG (from step 7)
6 into triplicate 0.2 mL PCR tubes.

7 9. Incubate each triplicate in a set temperature gradient (10-90 $^{\circ}$ C, incrementing
8 steps of 5 $^{\circ}$ C) in a gradient thermal cycler, for 10 min. Cool immediately after
9 incubation by returning the tubes to ice. **CRITICAL STEP:** The selection of
10 temperatures can be adjusted depending on the available amount of sample.

11 10. Centrifuge samples at 5,000g using a Beckman coulter table top centrifuge at 4
12 $^{\circ}$ C for 45 min.

13 11. Carefully transfer 80 μ L of the supernatant into a 96-well black plate and
14 measure GFP fluorescence emission at 512 nm by excitation at 488 nm in a
15 microplate spectrofluorometer. **CRITICAL STEP:** Aspirating 80 μ L gives a
16 good margin to avoid aspirating precipitated protein aggregates, however, if
17 necessary, a smaller volume of ca. 50 μ L can be aspirated.

18 12. Plot the values of GFP-fluorescence against the respective temperature and
19 calculate the melting temperature of the target-GFP fusion, using a sigmoidal 4-
20 parameter logistic function in GraphPad Prism or an equivalent graphing
21 program. For data normalization, set the highest and lowest data points of the
22 set as 100% and 0% respectively. **CRITICAL STEP:** GFP has a melting
23 temperature of 76 $^{\circ}$ C, above which it no longer fluoresces. Therefore, only
24 proteins with a melting temperature less than 76 $^{\circ}$ C can be routinely analyzed
25 using the GFP-TS assay.? **TROUBLESHOOTING**

26

27 **Screening of ligand libraries using detergent-solubilized membranes**

28 *Assessing solvent-induced effects on target protein stability* • Timing 2 h 30 min

29 13. Prepare a series of stock solvent concentrations, ensuring that you have enough
30 stock for triplicate reactions (10 μ L of each stock will be used in the reaction
31 mix). The span of solvent concentrations to be tested depends on the solvent
32 chosen in the intended ligand screen.

- 1 14. Aliquot 10 μL of each solvent stock into triplicate 0.2 mL PCR tubes. In parallel,
2 set up solvent-free controls in triplicate and add 10 μL water to them.
- 3 15. Adjust total membrane concentration to 3.5 mg/mL by addition of GFP-TS
4 reaction buffer. Solubilize under mild agitation for 1 h at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. **CRITICAL**
5 **STEP:** The required amount of detergent-solubilized membranes is 98 μL per
6 sample.
- 7 16. Aliquot 98 μL of the solubilized protein sample into the tubes containing the
8 solvent.
- 9 17. Add 12 μL OG stock (for a final concentration of 1% w/v) into each sample.
- 10 18. Heat the tubes at the determined T_m of the untreated protein from step 12 (plus
11 a triplicate set at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) for 10 min using a thermal cycler. Cool immediately by
12 returning the tubes to ice.
- 13 19. Centrifuge samples at 5,000g using a Beckman coulter table top centrifuge at 4
14 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 45 min.
- 15 20. Carefully transfer 80 μL of each supernatant into a 96-well black plate and
16 measure GFP fluorescence as described in Step 11.
- 17 21. Plot the GFP-fluorescence values for the heat-treated samples and compare with
18 the control sample without solvent. For data normalization, set the fluorescence
19 value of the solvent-free sample as 100%.

20

21 **Heating temperature optimization before ligand screening • Timing 2 h 30**
22 **min**

- 23 22. Aliquot 10 μL of the solvent stock (Use the concentration determined in steps
24 13-21) into triplicate 0.2 mL PCR tubes.
- 25 23. Adjust total membrane concentration to 3.5 mg/mL in 3 mL by addition of GFP-
26 TS reaction buffer. Solubilize under mild agitation for 1 h at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.
- 27 24. Aliquot 98 μL of the solubilized protein sample into the tubes containing the
28 solvent.
- 29 25. Add 12 μL OG stock (for a final concentration of 1% w/v) into each sample and
30 mix carefully.

- 1 26. Heat the tubes at set temperatures (ranging from $T_m - 6$ °C to $T_m + 6$ °C
2 increasing in 2 °C increments, plus a triplicate set at 4 °C) for 10 min in a
3 gradient thermal cycler. Cool immediately by returning the tubes to ice.
- 4 27. Centrifuge samples at 5,000g using a Beckman coulter table top centrifuge at 4
5 °C for 45 min.
- 6 28. Transfer 80 µL of each supernatant into a 96-well black plate and measure GFP
7 fluorescence as described in Step 11.
- 8 29. Plot the values of GFP-fluorescence from the heated samples against the control
9 sample incubated at 4 °C. For data normalization, set the fluorescence value of
10 the 4°C sample as 100%. **CRITICAL STEP:** The temperature which resulted
11 in a reduction of GFP-fluorescence by 30 – 50 % compared to the 4 °C control
12 should be the temperature used for subsequent ligand screening.

13

14 *Compound library ligand screening* • Timing 3 h 30 min + 30 min/ 96 ligands

- 15 30. Aliquot the ligands in 0.2 mL PCR tubes. For the control samples, aliquot
16 solvent volume equal to that of the dispensed ligands. If library size and
17 availability is not a limiting factor, setup of each reaction in triplicate is
18 recommended. **CRITICAL STEP:** The required amount of detergent-
19 solubilized membranes is roughly 108 µL per sample.?

20 **TROUBLESHOOTING**

- 21 31. Adjust total membrane concentration to 3.5 mg/mL by addition of GFP-TS
22 reaction buffer. Solubilize under mild agitation for 1 h at 4 °C.
- 23 32. Aliquot the solubilized protein material into the tubes containing the respective
24 ligands. **CRITICAL STEP:** Calculate the amount of solubilized sample to be
25 aliquoted by subtracting the volume of dispensed ligand and OG added from the
26 total volume of 120 µL.
- 27 33. Incubate the samples for 1 h in ice. **CRITICAL STEP:** The incubation time
28 may vary depending on parameters such as protein and ligand concentration.
29 We recommend up to a 1 h incubation prior to step 34.
- 30 34. Add 12 µL OG stock (for a final concentration of 1% w/v) into each sample and
31 mix carefully by pipetting.

- 1 35. Heat the tubes at the optimal heating temperature determined at Step 20 for 10
2 min in a thermal cycler. Cool immediately by returning the tubes to ice.
- 3 36. Centrifuge samples at 5,000g using a Beckman coulter table top centrifuge at 4
4 °C for 45 min.
- 5 37. Transfer 80 µL of each supernatant to a 96-well black plate and measure GFP
6 fluorescence as described in Step 11.
- 7 38. Plot the values obtained from the ligand-containing samples against the solvent-
8 only control. For data normalization, set the fluorescence value of the solvent-
9 only sample as 100%.

10 **CRITICAL STEP:** Using crude detergent-solubilized membranes allows for
11 screening in more native-like conditions, without the need of purified material.
12 However, certain ligands may interact with proteins present in the membranes and
13 even be modified, thus reducing the concentration of ligand available for interaction
14 with the target. If this is a concern, the ligand screen could instead be performed
15 using purified protein. **? TROUBLESHOOTING**

16

17 **Determination of ligand binding affinity • Timing 3 h 15 min**

- 18 39. Generate a series of stock ligand concentrations, ensuring that enough of each
19 stock is available to use 10 µL in the reaction mix (for triplicate reactions). If
20 solvent tolerance is a problem, smaller volumes of more concentrated ligand
21 stocks can be used. The respective ligand concentration to be tested varies on
22 an individual target-protein basis. Generally, a span of 0-10 mM is
23 recommended, but lower concentrations may be used when ligand solubility
24 and/or availability limits exist, e.g. when compound availability is scarce, when
25 using compound libraries with a uniform concentration, and/or when restricted
26 by solvent tolerance of the target. **? TROUBLESHOOTING**
- 27 40. Aliquot 10 µL of each ligand stock solution into triplicate sets of 0.2 mL PCR
28 tubes, with increasing ligand concentrations. In parallel, prepare a ligand free
29 control by adding 10 µL of solvent stock in place of the ligand stock for an
30 identical final solvent concentration.
- 31 41. Adjust total membrane concentration to 3.5 mg/mL by addition of GFP-TS
32 reaction buffer and solubilize under mild agitation at 4 °C for 1 h.

- 1 42. Aliquot 98 μL of the solubilized protein sample in the tubes containing the
- 2 ligands and mix carefully.
- 3 43. Incubate the protein-ligand samples at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 h.
- 4 44. Add 12 μL OG stock (for a final concentration of 1% w/v) and mix samples
- 5 carefully.
- 6 45. Heat the tubes at the optimal heating temperature determined at Step 20) for 10
- 7 min in a thermal cycler. Cool immediately by returning the tubes to ice.
- 8 46. Centrifuge samples at 5,000g using a Beckman coulter table top centrifuge at 4
- 9 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 45 min.
- 10 47. Remove 80 μL of the supernatant and measure GFP fluorescence as described
- 11 in Step 11.
- 12 48. Plot the values of GFP-fluorescence of each sample against the respective ligand
- 13 concentration and fit the data points using an appropriate non-linear regression
- 14 binding function in GraphPad Prism, e.g., a one site-total binding equation.

15 **Mutation analysis of ligand-binding site residues • Timing 3 h 40 min**

- 16 49. Adjust total membrane concentration to 3.5 mg/mL in 13 mL (subtract ligand
- 17 and OG volume which will be added in later steps) by addition of GFP-TS
- 18 reaction buffer. Solubilize under mild agitation for 1 h at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.
- 19 50. Divide the solubilized material into two aliquots of equal volume.
- 20 51. Add 65 μL of ligand stock to one aliquot, and an equal volume of solvent to the
- 21 other.
- 22 52. Incubate both aliquots at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 h.
- 23 53. Repeat the T_m measurement as described in steps 6-12.
- 24 54. Calculate the ΔT_m of each mutant construct by comparing the individual T_m
- 25 values in absence and presence of ligand. **CRITICAL STEP:** When analyzing
- 26 amino acid variants in a given target, it is possible that the T_m of the mutant(s)
- 27 is different from the T_m of the initial construct. Therefore, calculating ΔT_m (by
- 28 comparing the values of ligand-free and ligand-present states) is more accurate
- 29 for assessing the effects of mutations on ligand-binding.

30
31

1 **Measuring melting temperature of DDM purified GFP-fusions • Timing 2 h**

2 **CRITICAL:** The following steps describe procedures for performing melting T_m
3 measurements on purified target protein, which are very similar to those outlined
4 for detergent-solubilized membranes. Using purified protein is required when
5 screening for specific lipid-protein interactions, or if the fluorescent signal needs
6 to be higher to accurately monitor ligand interactions. The GFP-fluorescence
7 intensity should result in a signal to noise ratio greater than ten (recommended
8 target protein concentration ~0.01-0.03 mg/mL).

- 9 55. Adjust target protein to ~0.01-0.03 mg/mL in 6.5 mL (subtract OG volume) SEC
10 buffer.
11 56. Add 650 μ L OG stock (final 1% w/v) and mix sample carefully by inverting the
12 tube.
13 57. Repeat steps 8-12.

14

15 **Screening of stabilizing lipids with purified GFP-fusion • Timing 1 h 30 min**

- 16 58. Follow steps 22-29 (with addition of DDM instead of solvent) to determine the
17 optimal heating temperature of the protein-lipid mix. **CRITICAL STEP:** Lipid
18 stocks are prepared by solubilization in 10 % (w/v) DDM overnight under mild
19 agitation at 4 °C, and are diluted 10-fold in the protein solution (final
20 concentration of DDM 1% w/v). Consequently, the control samples must
21 contain 1% (w/v) DDM.
22 59. Aliquot 12 μ L of each lipid stock into triplicate 0.2 mL PCR tubes. Aliquot an
23 equal volume of 10% (w/v) DDM stock to the control tubes.
24 60. Based on the GFP-fluorescence intensity determined in Step 55, adjust target
25 protein to ~0.01-0.03 mg/mL in SEC buffer.
26 61. Aliquot 96 μ L of protein solution from step 59 into the tubes and mix carefully
27 by pipetting.
28 62. Add 12 μ L of OG stock (final concentration 1% (w/v)) and mix carefully.
29 63. Incubate each triplicate set at the optimal heating temperature (determined at
30 step 20 for detergent-solubilized membranes) for 10 min using a thermal cycler.
31 Cool immediately after incubation by returning the tubes to ice.

- 1 64. Centrifuge samples at 5,000g using a Beckman coulter table top centrifuge at 4
2 °C for 45 min.
- 3 65. Carefully transfer 80 µL of the supernatant into a 96-well black plate and
4 measure GFP fluorescence as described at Step 11.
- 5 66. Plot the values of GFP-fluorescence from the lipid-containing samples against
6 the DDM-only control. For data normalization, set the fluorescence value of the
7 DDM-only sample as 100%.

8

9 **TROUBLESHOOTING**

10

11 Troubleshooting advice can be found in Table 2.

12

13 **TIMING**

14

15 Steps 1-5, Confirming GFP-fusion quality: ~2h 30 min

16 Steps 6-12, Determining melting temperature in crude detergent-solubilized
17 membranes: ~3 h

18 Steps 13-21, Assessing solvent-induced effects on target protein stability: ~ 2 h 30 min

19 Steps 22-29, Heating temperature optimization before ligand screening: ~ 2 h 30 min

20 Steps 30-38, Compound library ligand screening: ~ 3 h 30 min + 30 min per 96 ligands

21 Steps 39-48, Determination of ligand binding affinity: ~ 3 h 15 min

22 Steps 49-54, Mutation analysis of ligand-binding site residues: ~ 3 h 40 min

23 Steps 55-57, Measuring melting temperature of DDM purified GFP-fusions: ~ 2 h

24 Steps 58-66, Screening of stabilizing lipids with purified GFP-fusions: ~ 1h 30 min

25

26

27

1 ANTICIPATED RESULTS

2 We have performed the GFP-TS assay using crude membrane material and purified
3 sample in detergent for several SLC transporters^{27,28}. Using crude detergent-solubilized
4 membranes, we demonstrate here that the GFP-TS assay can discriminate the binding
5 of the substrate nucleotide CMP to *human* CMP-sialic acid transporter (CST) SLC35A1
6 from the closely related non-substrate nucleotide UMP, and 192 nucleoside-analogues
7 in a 96-well format (Fig. 4a, b). We confirm that 0.5 mM of CMP stabilizes human
8 SLC35A1 by ΔT_m of 5 °C (Fig. 4c), as visually apparent when one compares the FSEC
9 traces of sample heated to a temperature of 40 °C with and without the nucleotide
10 present (Fig. 4d). Using *human* SLC35A1 as a control, we have further shown that the
11 plant homologue from *Zea mays* is specifically stabilized by the nucleotide
12 monophosphate CMP, and is therefore almost certainly a transporter for CMP-sialic
13 acid^{27,28}. It was later confirmed that the plant homologue could transport CMP-sialic
14 acid (in exchange for CMP) by proteoliposome-based transport assays using
15 radiolabeled substrates²⁸. Owing to the challenges associated with setting up
16 proteoliposome-based assays^{11,17}, and the limited availability of labelled compounds,
17 the GFP-TS assay is an important stepping stone to in-depth functional characterization.

18

19 The GFP-TS was further utilized with crude detergent solubilized membranes to
20 determine the CMP binding affinities (K_d) for *plant* and *human* CST, which were found
21 to be consistent with each other and to isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC)
22 measurements from the purified proteins²⁷ (Fig. 4e). Interestingly, CMP-sialic acid was
23 found to bind with much lower affinity than CMP, and we could therefore only obtain
24 a K_d value using the GFP-TS as the signal was too weak for ITC (Fig. 4f); the
25 differences between CMP and CMP-sialic acid binding affinities were further
26 consistent with IC_{50} value differences²⁸.

27 Membrane protein crystals grown *in meso* or using the lipidic cubic phase (LCP)
28 method generally produce higher resolution structures, as they have a lower solvent
29 content (type I crystals) than those grown by traditional vapor-diffusion crystallization
30 (type II crystals)⁵⁰. To grow LCP crystals of membrane proteins, the purified membrane
31 protein solution is mixed with the synthetic lipid monoolein⁵¹. Using the GFP-TS assay,
32 we added monoolein to purified transporters, and found that the monoolein lipid was in

1 fact very destabilizing for most of the eukaryotic membrane proteins tested including
2 plant CST²⁷. To compensate, we found that if CMP was added during *in meso* based
3 crystallization of plant CST we could improve its stability and enable the formation of
4 LCP crystals which were used to determine the structure by X-ray crystallography²⁸.
5 We next employed the GFP-TS assay to carry out extensive mutagenesis-based analysis
6 of the CMP binding site of *plant* CST (Fig. 5a–c) in parallel with *human* CST (Fig. 5d–
7 e). Importantly, all CMP and CMP-sialic acid binding measurements could be carried
8 using small amounts of crude detergent solubilized membranes, and would have
9 otherwise been more expensive and time-consuming if each mutant needed to be
10 purified in sufficient amounts for binding analysis using most other methods, such as
11 ITC.

12

13 Lipids are of critical importance to membrane protein function³⁸, and yet molecular
14 details are often difficult to obtain due to their hydrophobic nature and weak
15 interactions with membrane proteins. Although FSEC-TS was shown to detect the
16 binding of ligands and drugs to channels and transporters e.g.,^{22,52}, it was unclear if it
17 could detect specific lipid interactions. We recently confirmed that FSEC-TS could be
18 used to detect such specific interactions, demonstrating that the lipid cardiolipin binds
19 to the bacterial Na⁺/H⁺ antiporter NhaA from *E. coli* and not to its close homologue
20 NapA from *Thermus thermophilus*²⁷, both of which observations were originally
21 reported by native MS measurements^{53,54} (Fig. 6a–d). We were able to support this
22 finding by generating a monomeric mutant of NhaA, which no longer binds to
23 cardiolipin, thus does not show the cardiolipin-driven dimerization of wild type
24 NhaA²⁷. More recently, we reported the structure of the mammalian Na⁺/H⁺ exchanger
25 SLC9A9 (NHE9), and studied its interactions with lipids using native MS (Fig. 6e)⁴³.
26 However, native MS could only estimate potential lipid interactions, whereas with
27 FSEC-TS we confirmed the specific lipid-binding interactions of PIP₂₍₃₎ lipids that were
28 consistent with the masses detected by native MS (Fig. 6e–g)⁴³. The PIP₂₍₃₎ binding
29 could be abolished by mutagenesis of several NHE9 residues as confirmed by
30 combining thermostability and native MS measurements⁴³. Our results suggest that the
31 negatively charged lipids cardiolipin and PIP₂ bind to NhaA and NHE9, respectively,
32 to stabilize the functional homodimer⁴³. Here, we show that GFP-TS gives comparable
33 results to FSEC-TS for cardiolipin binding to NhaA or PIP₂ binding to SLC9A9 (Fig.

1 6c, g, h). In a more high-throughput manner we have used GFP-TS to screen for the
2 lipid binding preference of SLC transporters and several bacterial homologues²⁷.
3 Surprisingly, we found that, on average, the melting temperatures of SLC transporters
4 and the bacterial homologues were similar prior to purification²⁷. Destabilization of the
5 SLC transporters was more apparent upon purification, but could be recovered again
6 by the addition of specific lipids²⁷. Our results suggest that the GFP-TS assay can
7 identify lipids that recover lipid-specific stabilization of SLC transporters, which is lost
8 during the de-lipidation process of protein purification.

9

10 Taken together, the GFP-TS assay is a valuable tool in the effort to functionally
11 characterize SLC transporters and their interaction with inhibitors and lipids for
12 establishing important mechanistic details. While our focus has been on the use of the
13 GFP-TS assay for transporters produced in *S. cerevisiae*, we see no reason why the
14 described methodology cannot be utilized for screening ligand and lipid interactions to
15 other membrane protein families using protein produced from other GFP-based
16 expression and screening platforms, e.g.,^{45,55}.

17

18 **Data availability**

19 All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article.

20

21

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 2 **Figure 2. Development and validation of the GFP-TS assay.** a, GFP fluorescence of
 3 DDM-solubilized membranes containing a bacterial homologue of the Apical Sodium
 4 dependent Bile acid Transporter from *Neisseria meningitis* (ASBT_{NM})-GFP remaining
 5 in solution after heating and centrifugation (cyan circles), measured using a 96-well
 6 plate spectrofluorometer. The fluorescence from the respective pellets resuspended in
 7 identical volumes of buffer to the supernatant are also shown (black squares). Apparent
 8 T_m values were calculated using data from the nine different temperatures and fitted to
 9 a sigmoidal dose–response equation (bars show the range of two technical replicates,
 10 and values reported are mean ± s.e.m. of the fit). b, FSEC-TS traces of the ASBT_{NM}-

1 GFP supernatants from **a**; the aggregates are highlighted by the dotted ellipse, and the
2 corresponding FSEC-TS melting curve is shown as an inset. **c**, As in **a** except that the
3 detergent OG was added to the DDM-solubilized ASBT_{NM}-GFP samples prior to
4 heating (bars show the range of two technical replicates, and values reported are mean
5 $\pm$ s.e.m. of the fit; T_m values are tabulated in Table 1. **d**, As in **b** except that the detergent
6 OG was added to the DDM-solubilized ASBT_{NM}-GFP samples prior to heating. The
7 position of the aggregates removed by addition OG is indicated by a dotted ellipse and
8 the corresponding FSEC-TS melting curve as an inset. **e**, Sensitivity of the GFP-TS
9 assay to free GFP. FSEC profiles of detergent-solubilized ASBT_{NM}-GFP were
10 measured in the presence of increasing concentrations of free GFP and the apparent T_m
11 values were determined by GFP-TS. The percentage of free GFP fluorescence is
12 expressed as a fraction of the total protein sample fluorescence measured on a plate
13 reader. **f**. Apparent T_m values determined for detergent-solubilized membrane fractions
14 of different membrane proteins expressed as GFP-fusions (x-axis labels) without OG
15 (open bars), and FSEC-TS values from the same samples (filled bars). FI, fluorescence
16 intensity.

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2 **Figure 3. Optimization of the GFP-TS assay.** **a**, Schematic representation of the GFP-
 3 TS assay. Apparent T_m of a membrane protein (MP) in detergent-solubilized membranes
 4 can easily be calculated from the fluorescence signal of detergent-solubilized GFP-
 5 fusions remaining in the solution after heating and centrifugation. **b**, Correlation of
 6 thermostability as assessed by comparing the half-life obtained using the CPM assay
 7 on DDM-purified fusions in the detergent n-Dodecyl-N, N-Dimethylamine-N-Oxide
 8 (LDAO) versus T_m values based on the GFP-TS assay performed on non-purified GFP
 9 fusions in DDM and OG. (figure taken from Nji et. al (2018)²⁷. **c**, Apparent T_m
 10 measured by GFP-TS for detergent-solubilized hCST-GFP membranes in heating block
 11 (black squares) and thermal cycler (magenta circles) format. **d**, Effect of increasing

1 DMSO concentration on signal from detergent solubilized hCST-GFP membranes.
2 Values of the heated samples (filled bars) are normalized against the non-heated control
3 sample with 0 % (v/v) DMSO (empty bar). Data were obtained from two independent
4 experiments. **e**, Optimization of assay temperature for optimal signal intensity from
5 detergent solubilized hCST-GFP membranes. The intensity values obtained from two
6 independent experiments were normalized against the non-heated control sample kept
7 at 4°C (empty bar). The red box indicates the suitable temperature range to assay,
8 resulting in 20-40% of the original non-heated control intensity. **f**, In some cases, due
9 to low expression levels, it might be necessary to concentrate the sample and thus
10 increase the total protein-GFP fluorescence by increasing the membrane to detergent
11 ratio. The apparent T_m values for detergent-solubilized ASBT_{NM}-GFP using GFP-TS
12 only differ by 1.5 °C over a total membrane protein concentration range of 3.0 to 7.5
13 mg/ml.

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2 **Figure 4. GFP-TS assay for functional characterization of human CMP-sialic acid**
3 **transporter (hCST) and deorphanization of a plant homologue. a,** Screening a
4 nucleoside-analogue library screen for binding to the human CMP-sialic acid
5 transporter (hCST)-GFP using GFP-TS. Mean supernatant fluorescence after heating at
6 $T_m + 5^\circ\text{C}$ for binding to the solvent control (DMSO, 1.2% v/v, blue circles), 0.12 mM
7 CMP (green circles), 0.12 mM UMP (magenta circles), and 0.12 mM of the 192
8 nucleoside-analogue library (black circles). Error bars represent the range of each value
9 averaged between three independent experiments. **b,** Box and whiskers representation
10 of ligand screening data shown in **a.** Median is shown as a line, bottom and top

1 boundaries represent lower and upper quartiles, respectively. Whiskers show the
2 minimum and maximum mean value of each group. **c**, Apparent T_m determined using
3 GFP-TS for hCST-GFP membranes without (black circles) and after (green squares)
4 addition of 0.5 mM CMP. **d**, FSEC profiles of hCST-GFP heated at 40 °C in absence
5 (black line) and in presence (green line) of 0.5 mM CMP. The samples were collected
6 from a 96-well plate after GFP-TS. **e**, **f**. Binding of CMP to *Zea mays* CMP-sialic acid
7 transporter (CST_{ZM})-GFP (black squares) and hCST-GFP (cyan circles) in membranes
8 (**e**) and CMP-sialic acid to purified CST_{ZM}-GFP (black squares) and hCST-GFP (cyan
9 circles) (**f**) as monitored by GFP-TS. Binding affinities (K_d) were calculated from data
10 points recorded over a range of CMP and CMP-Sialic acid concentrations, and these
11 were fitted by non-linear regression using a one site-total binding function. Respective
12 K_d values obtained by isothermal titration calorimetry (ITC) are shown in parenthesis.
13 Data show mean $\pm$ s.e.m from 3 independent experiments. Figures adapted from; (**e**)
14 Nji et al. (2018)²⁷ and (**f**) Nji et al. (2019)²⁸.

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1 **Figure 5. GFP-TS assay for ligand interaction studies to human SLC35A1 and a**
2 **plant homologue. a,** The substrate-binding site of CST_{ZM} in the outward-facing
3 conformation (PDB id: 6I1R). Transmembrane segments are shown in cartoon
4 representation colored brown. Water molecules are shown as brown spheres, CMP and
5 coordinating residues are shown as sticks. Putative hydrogen bonds are depicted as
6 dashed lines, as is the π -cation interaction between W209 and cytosine nucleobase. **b,**
7 Apparent T_m shift after addition of 1 mM CMP to WT (open bars) and CMP sialic-acid
8 (CMP-sia) binding residue mutants (filled bars) of CST_{ZM}. The mutated residues were
9 selected based on the substrate-binding site presented in (a). UMP was added to
10 measure non-specific binding (red bars). **c.** as (b) but with 1 mM CMP-sia as ligand,
11 and sialic acid added to measure non-specific binding (red bars) instead. **d.** as (b) but
12 with hCST. **e.** as (c) but with hCST. Data show mean $\pm$ s.e.m from 3 independent
13 experiments. Figure adapted from Nji et al. (2019)²⁸.

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3 **Figure 6. Monitoring lipid-protein interactions with FSEC-TS and GFP-TS. a, b.**

4 Native MS data show that *E. coli* NhaA appears almost exclusively as a monomer

5 following detergent removal, in line with the sparse subunit contacts in the crystal

6 structure (PDB id: 4AU5) (inset) and *T. thermophilus* NapA appears as an intact dimer

7 following release from detergent micelles, in agreement with the crystal structure (PDB

1 id: 5BZ3) (inset). Lipid adducts are shown as red dots. **c.** Apparent T_m values for
2 purified *E. coli* NhaA-GFP as obtained by FSEC-TS and GFP-TS in absence (black
3 circles and squares) and presence (cyan and green squares) of 3 mg/mL cardiolipin
4 (CDL) 18:1. **d.** Apparent T_m values for purified *T. thermophilus* NapA-GFP as obtained
5 by FSEC-TS in absence (black circles) and presence (cyan squares) of 3 mg/mL
6 cardiolipin (CDL) 18:1. **e.** MS of *horse* NHE9 residues 8-574 (NHE9*) purified in the
7 absence of additional brain lipids. Without brain lipid addition, *horse* NHE9 appears as
8 sharp peaks, revealing several adducts of approximately 1 kDa each, as well as a minor
9 monomer population. **f.** Thermal stabilization of purified NHE9* by lipids. Data
10 presented are mean values $\pm$ value range of $n = 4$ experiments. **g.** Apparent thermal shift
11 stabilization of purified NHE9* in the presence of 1 mg/mL phosphatidylinositol bis-
12 4,5-phosphate,1,2-dioctanoyl (PIP₂) (red) compared to no-PIP₂ control (black). Data
13 presented are normalized mean FSEC peak fluorescence as mean values $\pm$ data range
14 of $n = 2$ technical repeats; the apparent T_m was calculated with a sigmoidal 4-parameter
15 logistic regression function; the average ΔT_m presented is calculated from $n = 2$
16 independent titrations. **h.** Thermal stabilization of NHE9* by PIP₂ as observed by GFP-
17 TS. Figures adapted from; **(a-b)** Landreh et al. (2017)⁵³ and **(e-g)** Winkelman et al.
18 (2020)⁴³.

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1 Table 1

Name	Function	Melting temperature, T_m (°C) FSEC-TS (+ β -OG)	Melting temperature, T_m (°C) GFP-TS (+ β -OG)	T_m difference (°C)
AmtB	Ammonium channel	77.4 ± 0.4	77.9 ± 0.3	+0.5
ASBT _{NM}	Bile acid transporter	50.6 ± 0.7	52.6 ± 0.4	+2.0
EmrD	Multidrug transporter	32.7 ± 0.8	34.8 ± 0.7	+2.1
GlpG	Rhomboid protease	61.7 ± 1.5	63.9 ± 0.5	+2.2
GlpT	Glycol-3-phosphate transporter	33.3 ± 0.4	35.9 ± 0.7	+2.6
Mhp1	Benzyl-hydantoin transporter	37.5 ± 0.5	41.0 ± 0.3	+3.5
LacY	Lactose permease	33.1 ± 0.1	35.7 ± 0.3	+2.6
NapA	Sodium/ proton antiporter	70.6 ± 0.2	72.1 ± 0.9	+1.5
NhaA	Sodium/ proton antiporter	38.4 ± 1.1	42.6 ± 1.2	+4.2
XylE	Xylose transporter	36.8 ± 1.6	40.6 ± 0.8	+3.8
rat GLUT5	Fructose transporter	26.7 ± 1.4 (32.8 ± 1.8) *	32.4 ± 1.5 (36.8 ± 0.7) *	+5.7 (+4.0) *
hCST	CMP-sialic acid transporter	32.4 ± 0.5	33.8 ± 0.6	+1.4
horse NHE9 (8-574)	Sodium/ proton antiporter	33.0 ± 0.8	33.5 ± 1.0	+0.5

2 * indicates 0.5 % OG present in the final volume of mixtures

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1 Table 2

Step	Problem	Possible reason	Solution
3	Too low GFP-fluorescence value (Signal to noise ratio <10)	Poor target expression	Increase total membrane concentration for solubilization up to 7.5 mg/ml and solubilize with 2% v/v DDM
4	A large aggregation peak on FSEC profile	Intrinsically unstable target protein and/or fraction of poorly folded target	1. Test different buffers, e.g., MES pH 6.5, HEPES pH 7.5, salt concentrations and/or add reducing agents. 2. Lower final concentration of OG to 0.5%. 3. Add final 0.2% cholesterol hemisuccinate (CHS).
4	Free GFP in the sample is greater than 30%	Protein degradation	Optimise construct or overexpression conditions
5	Non-specificity of testing compounds	Complexity of membrane composition	Use purified fusion protein
11	Melting curves not resulting in a sigmoidal profile	Protein inhomogeneity	Test different buffers such as MES pH 6.5, HEPES pH 7.5, salt concentrations and/or add reducing agents
29	Final ligand concentration will be less than 80 – 100 μ M	Availability and cost	Carry out GFP-TS (steps 29-34) in lower volume and add buffer (+OG) to a final of 120 μ L before step 35
38	T_m shift is less than 2 $^{\circ}$ C	Low affinity of ligand to target and/or binding mode does not cause conformational stabilization	1. Increase ligand concentration 2. Test different buffers e.g., MES pH 6.5, HEPES pH 7.5

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11 **Competing interests** The authors declare no competing interests.

1 **Additional information**

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